

THE PHYSICAL-EDUCATIONAL CONTENT OF DEVELOPING THE KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS ABOUT SPORTS AESTHETICS

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the development of knowledge about sports aesthetics in future physical education teachers, the practical methodical system of developing knowledge about sports aesthetics, and the effectiveness of developing knowledge about sports aesthetics have been studied. Motives for developing knowledge of sports aesthetics among future physical education teachers were also analyzed.

Key words: pedagogue, physical education, sports aesthetics, sport, technology, didactic, modernization, integration, cluster approach, fossilization education, reflexive, interactive, training, innovative, integrative.

INTRODUCTION.

Today, world scientists are conducting research on improving the scientific-methodical and organizational foundations of improving the professional knowledge, practical skills, and professional skills of physical education and sports specialists. An important aspect of these studies is that attention is paid to the cooperation of various fields in the training of sports specialists and the development of mass sports among the population. As a result, on the one hand, economic growth is increasing, and on the other hand, problems such as material interest becoming the main motive in the outlook of physical education and sports specialists, and recognizing physical strength as dominant, are emerging. This requires the organization of research related to the complex development of the way of thinking of future physical education and sports specialists.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

The research of the pedagogical and psychological foundations of the development of the knowledge of sports aesthetics in future physical education teachers can be classified into three parts: studying in Uzbekistan, CIS countries and Western countries.

Uzbek scientists N.N. Tokhtaboyev, A.N. Shopulatov, S.S. Tajibayev, F. Kerimov, A. Shopulatov, A. Muzaffarov, A. Mirzayev, A. Khudoyorov work on the development of professional skills of physical education and sports specialists, formation of moral values in athletes. issues of effective organization are studied. Also, the scientific researches of S.Kh. Fayzulina, S.K. Annamuratova, A. Hasanov, F. Zorayev, A. Vosikhov, A. Sulaymonov, K. Dosimov have highlighted the educational possibilities of aesthetic education and sports aesthetics.

In Western countries, the issues of directing young people to the process of mass sports rehabilitation, rational use of the possibilities of sports aesthetics and increasing the educational opportunities of physical education in this regard are discussed by scientists B. Lowe, H. Slyusher, F. Keenon, A. Vett, E. .Researched by Zadarko, J. Junger, Z. Barabas, D. Brown, A. Alpers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In aesthetic education of students during physical training, special attention is paid to their age characteristics, because adolescence is extremely complex and even somewhat unique from a social point of view. That is why an individual (one-on-one) and differentiated approach to adolescents is required. The importance of aesthetic education of students is constantly increasing. Because the aesthetic evaluation of sports is formed through physical education and is a necessary factor as the cause and regulator of attitude. Physical education also helps to form valuable aesthetic directions, develops aesthetic and creative abilities, activates the interest and need to engage in physical education and sports, activities dedicated to them.

The task of physical education with sports determines the social importance of this education, as well as its connection with moral and physical education. For this reason, students' interactions with each other and with adults (teachers, trainers, parents, others) are managed in aesthetic education. In this process, the spiritual world of students develops, and their objective attitude towards the environment is formed.

Sport - in all its forms, shows invaluable materials for aesthetic education. Because it contains professional skill, open passionate feeling, aesthetic processes that cause joy and pleasure. In order for aesthetic impressions to have a positive effect on the personality of students, their conscious interest in sports aesthetics is necessary, which, under appropriate conditions, turns into a holistic physical culture.

Any activity related to physical education is a complex process based on the expected passion, realized interest, certain knowledge, understanding and imagination about this culture, the most important thing is to make interest effective, to make it aspiration, interests is to turn it into a tendency to engage in activities that have become the center. Interesting historical sports materials, bright scenes from sports life, impressive works of art on the topic of sports, a kaleidoscope covering events, the life and work of famous athletes can arouse such interest in students and young people. Interesting materials on this topic can be the source of students' interest in sports aesthetics.

One of the important conditions for the aesthetic education of students in physical education classes and extracurricular activities is to raise their interest in sports aesthetics to the level of need. At the same time, in order to cover all aspects of students' lives and activities, it is necessary to provide opportunities for developing spiritual-aesthetic and, of course, physical abilities. After all, aesthetic education by means of physical education does not imply one-sidedness, but the use of all factors aimed at forming perfection.

A number of factors contribute to the interest in sports aesthetics

- background, environment, knowledge-understanding, influence of the material on the cognitive-cognitive sphere of the student's personality, first of all, it requires the motivational influence of social-personal orientation.

Interest in sports aesthetics is activated by perceiving and evaluating sports aesthetics in any type of sport, performing exercises and actions on the elements of aesthetic expression, and applying acquired skills and competencies. Here, passion is activated and stabilized as an interest arising under certain psychological and pedagogical influence.

Considering interest as a meaning, psychological and social concept, it is possible to form a description of sports aesthetics on the basis of studying its characteristics, content and description, types and functionality. It is an organizational and voluntary desire to master

sports as a whole, including the object of aesthetic interest, to express oneself, to make a decision - to enjoy and enjoy it (emotional-social self-expression).

The skills acquired in physical training, in selected sports - the need and ability to further increase knowledge, skills and abilities in sports, as well as the conscious attitude and activity of a person to increase his external beauty as a classification of sports aesthetics can be interpreted. In this way, the main indicators of interest in sports aesthetics were determined: a positive, social and personal reason; to find - to know; evaluator-oriented; needy-active.

Such enthusiasm for sports aesthetics is important for the development of not only physical culture, but also general culture of students. Interest in sports aesthetics consists in mastering the indicated skills and abilities, looking at the methods, introducing and activating students with the variety of tasks related to exercises, films, interests and abilities. A persuasive conversation rich in clear content and information and memorable visual and pictorial (illustrated) material are important in this.

The following requirements are set for a conversation that activates interest in sports aesthetics among future physical education teachers: age appropriateness; attractiveness; the ability to know and understand - bright, unforgettable content with aesthetic expression, visual-pictorial, high-quality materials, covering modern information; a conversation with a clear goal and an explained task, the main thing is to explain it with specific evidence; supporting sincere and emotional feedback of students; comfortable (comfortable) environment; it is advisable to follow a personal one-on-one approach to teenagers.

Combining sports aesthetics with art gives a very effective result. Because, according to their characteristics, sport and art are inextricably linked. This relationship can be observed in various forms of art: theater (stage) plastic, athletics (ballet); in acrobatics (circus art), which are very beautiful and complex in terms of courage, etc. At the moment, the depiction of sports as a visual plot in theater, cinema, and visual arts means that sports and art are closely related. They can be generally described as sports aesthetics.

The feeling of beauty in sports strengthens the interest in it, and the perception of beauty in sports makes it more understandable and stable. Interest in sports aesthetics is activated by complex methods, original methods, various tools, and they, if they help to connect lessons with extracurricular activities, naturally form an integrated system with a certain purpose and meaning. This is one of the most effective forms of aesthetic education.

Interest is the main component of aesthetic education. It is activated and constantly supported with the help of special educational and training tools. Only then, on the basis of students' interest in sports aesthetics, aesthetic education will reach its highest level. In this process, interest provides the most important foundation in the personality of students: culture, the world of thought, including sports aesthetics; the speed of aesthetic perception, sports beauty, analytical ability and valuable directions in general, especially in sports; creative ability; communicative need; the need for physical development and independent study, and most importantly, they enrich the spiritual world, as a result of which all-round development occurs, free time is pleasant and useful, which is a social order of our society, country, and government.

The social nature of the problem can be explained by the following factors. As we mentioned, physical culture, precisely culture, that is, formation of a beautiful figure, has been one of the main conditions for the education of a perfect personality. Such demand of the

society to its members has not lost its social force even today. Therefore, the desire for aesthetic culture through physical exercises is observed at all stages of the development of human society. This aspect confirms that it is a social phenomenon.

Also, at each stage of society's development, a social order appropriate and specific to this stage is given. The "executor" of this order, and the education of the requested person is dealt with by the science of pedagogy. In the development of any society and country, its competent members play a decisive role. In this regard, sports and art are of special importance. Elements of sports aesthetics are formed at the points of their connection with each other.

Physical education and sports give a person good mood, aesthetic spirit, mobility, dexterity, agility, physical activity. In this regard, B. Lowe in his book "The Beauty of Sports" wrote F. Keenon's "Theatre, an art form that develops based on the audience... At sports competitions, the audience behaves as if they were watching a performance: they applaud the people with high skills and they do not hide their negative attitude towards the poor performer. "We talk about 'game' both in sports and in the theater," he says, referring to the moral-aesthetic educational value of sports. Also, in the book "Sports and Existence" by B. Low H. Slusher, "Sport is a real sport, it can achieve aesthetic quality and elegance. It is a state rich in deep meaning for an athlete... sport requires inner integrity and a high level of emotional upliftment," says H. Slusher, emphasizing the aesthetic pleasure that an athlete feels. It is also clear that training the ability to feel physical beauty in a sports person plays a big role in his development. The work carried out in this field is aimed at the formation of physical beauty and a healthy lifestyle of a healthy and well-rounded generation.

Philosopher and scientist T. Mahmudov states that "Physical culture, in a broad sense, is a process that realizes all the natural and social abilities of a person, and makes him more and more humanized and elevated"³. Here we are not talking about the requirements for the physical culture of a professional athlete, but about a healthy person who is distinguished by natural mobility, good stature, and physical qualities. Therefore, health is an invaluable wealth, the basis for creating material and spiritual blessings, and a component of human perfection, which is considered the highest value. As the first President I.A. Karimov noted, a person with a high physical culture "will not have dissatisfaction with life, pain and envy towards others, his heart and soul will be clean." In this sense, providing physical maturity with spiritual and spiritual wealth is the basis of our national development. A mentally and physically healthy person has opportunities to realize his creative abilities, has a high mood and is creative. This is evident not only in the field of physical labor, but also in his activity in creating aesthetic values.

CONCLUSION. In increasing the prestige of new Uzbekistan in the world community, along with all spheres of science and technology, culture, art, and sports, the role and prestige of culture stand out. Therefore, the interest in sports among students is increasing sharply. Enriching the content and direction of this interest as an important means of education, achieving aesthetic education as well as physical maturity at its base, the rational use of sports aesthetics indicators as a socio-pedagogical problem requires special research and socio-pedagogical becomes regular as a problem. After all, society and humanity are constantly developing, so the science of pedagogy continues to solve new problems for each of its stages. Aesthetic education of students in physical education lessons and extracurricular activities is

also a component of the system of socio-pedagogical problems. After all, each of the elements of this system and complex has its place in the education of a well-rounded person.

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